

Research

Measure the Impact of a bank development on the economic growth in Yemen by using Form "ARDL"

Adnan Alsanoy^{1*}, Mona Alariqi², Maniyassouwe Amana², Farhan Aslam³

¹Sana'a University, Yemen

²Wuhan University of Technology, Wuhan, China

³ Management services wing, Establishment Division Islamabad, Pakistan

***Corresponding author:**

M.Alariqi

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Abstract: This study aims to measure the impact of the of a bank development on the economic growth in the Republic of Yemen represented by the Cooperative and Agricultural Credit Bank, through which a set of indicators were used, including customer deposits total , loans Total, financing facilities and activities, in addition to the bank's balances total in other banks, all in real prices as an indicator of banking development, as GDP used in real prices as an indicator of economic growth, and this study used the standard method of self-regression of the distributed lag ARDL and one of the most prominent results was that system of Yemeni banking, represented by the Cooperative and Agricultural Credit Bank, could not play an effective role in encouraging economic growth in Yemen. Therefore, it is necessary to take targeted policies that seek to activate the role of the banking system in the overall process of economic development in Yemen, the most important of which are: Activating and developing the role of the private sector in the economy, mitigating the role of the informal economic activities of the private sector in the economy, Reducing restrictions on the banking system which mean freeing the banking system from all financial restraint policies, in addition to achieving security and political stability in Yemen, and developing banking operations systems in line with a new Situation of economic in the country and amending the terms and rates for loan granting.

Keywords: bank development, Economic growth, Yemen, ARDL

Introduction

Banking systems are one of the most important systems in any economic structures which in they play main role in financial intermediation between places of surplus and deficit in the national economy as a whole, and the formation of capital is a prerequisite for economic growth. So, the underdeveloped financial systems of developing countries consider capital formation difficult to achieve.

One of the most important goals of economic policies is to raise the standard of living for individuals and increase their welfare within societies. This is what most countries seek by increasing real individual income, which is the most important indicator of economic growth for any country. Here, the banking sector plays a vital role in financing the economy of any country. And the role of the banking sector in development is evident through the financing provides to form capital for projects in all fields, and its ability to mobilize deposits as it plays the role of intermediary between borrowers and depositors, which will help in economic growth if it is submitted to establish investment projects and this will lead to economic expansion in all fields.

And considering that banks are the backbone of the economy as the main channel for flowing of capital and its role in supporting the economy, the banks have been affected greatly according to these changes, as its most important manifestations were the trend towards liberalizing banking activity from restrictions, in addition to the recurrence of financial crises and increasing their severity, as it increased The trend towards expansion through banking merger, as the role of banks transformed from financial intermediation to inclusiveness, which enables them to carry out other activities such as insurance in addition to the emergence of new types of electronic services and others and advanced products that banks provide for society.

In light of these developments, banks became in a position to keep abreast of these developments and take advantage of advantages such as new innovative financial products and information technology with a focus on performance efficiency, and assessing the efficiency of banks and working on monitor their activity is necessary for the banks to remain risks and changes, so measure the efficiency of these Banks can know the strengths and weaknesses, and try to correct deviations and remedy the situation before it is too late, the development in operational efficiency measuring tools appears about the importance of positive performance in the banking industry, and this is evident through the development or improvement of many of the indicators Technologies to measure this efficiency.

Through this, the cooperative and agricultural credit bank was chosen to study its efficiency it's one of the important banks in Yemen, which passed several stages since its establishment until today, beginning of the merger stage between two banks to the stage of development and change from an agricultural bank to a comprehensive bank that includes all banking services, Each stage was different from the other, which we will address, it's not for the purpose of comparison, but to measure the development in the bank during the study period, which was in a period, the bank witnessed a major changes. Likewise, Yemen witnessed political events that had negative effects on the economic sector in general and on the banking sector in particular, The most recent of the events of 2011 and the successive political events that led to the instability of security, which had its effects on economic growth, which was reflected on banking growth and the period taken by the study from 1995 to 2015.

The study Problem:

The problem of the study is the low contribution of the banking system to financing economic in Yemen. A Yemeni economy suffers from the difficulty of obtaining sources of the economy financing and economic development achieving, and financing bank in the normal situation is very important, especially in increasing the rate of growth and progress at the economic level, it increases investment and increases production and then access to economic growth, and Yemeni bank financing remains limited due to the inability to control cash.

Therefore, it was necessary to clarify whether the cooperative and agricultural credit bank as one of the most important components of the Yemeni banking sector has an effective role in the economy financing and thus economic development, and through the foregoing the problem of the study in: what extent does the development of the cooperative and agricultural credit bank contribute to economic growth in the Republic of Yemen?

The hypothesis of the study:

The cooperative and agricultural credit bank has no impact on the economic growth represented by the gross domestic product in the Republic of Yemen.

Objectives of the study:

Measuring the impact of the Cooperative and Agricultural Credit Bank on the economic growth in the Republic of Yemen during the specified period in the study, and through this main aim the following aims have been graded: Study extent the development of the cooperative and agricultural credit bank using the ARDL form and study the relationship between important variables in the long and short term, Determining the degree of correlation and the relationship between bank credit granted to the private sector and the economic growth indicators represented by the gross domestic product, Evaluating the role of the Cooperative and Agricultural Credit Bank through study some of the expressed indicators. standing on the challenges and difficulties that may face the banking sector represented by the Cooperative and Agricultural Credit Bank in achieving economic growth, and Summarization conclusions and recommendations that are useful in studying economic policies to develop the banking system.

The importance of studying:

The importance of the study is demonstrated that the cooperative and agricultural credit bank and other specialized banks in the banking system are considered institutions that stimulate economic growth and show the relationship of the banking system to economic growth through the level of economic activity and its relationship to money and liquidity in society, which is the primary topic which is around monetary policy. If the amount of money in circulation has revolves, encouraged an increase in demand for goods and services and thus an increase in the size of the gross domestic product and the achievement of economic growth. Therefore, this monetary policy cannot properly perform its role except through an advanced banking system.

The importance of this study increases especially in the period ,which was conducted, which included two periods, the period before the transformation of the cooperative and agricultural credit bank from a specialized bank to a commercial bank and the current period which was not previously discussed, in addition to that this study used modern standard methods to help the leaders in the banking system to develop it, and the researcher believes that this study will represent a new and important addition in its field to the Yemeni library.

Study methodology:

The study will be based on a descriptive and standard statistical analysis to study the economic situation in Yemen in general, and on the reality of economic development and its indicators in Yemen by focusing on the reality of the agricultural credit bank and its development indicators and the extent of its contribution to economic growth, and the researcher has relied on time series data that includes data. The variables of this study, and to measure efficiency, the researcher followed the method of the Bounds Testing Approach for joint integration, which is based on the use of the Autoregressive Distributed Lag Model (ARDL) method, which is an impartial method that avoids many standard problems, etc. Plus, particularly reduction of views.

And the ARDL form can be applied by performing some tests, including Unit Root test to ensure the stability of time series, then the Wald test for joint integration in long-term to test for a long-term balance relationship between the variables, in addition to estimating the mistake correction form to detect the short-term relationship between the dependent variable and the independent variables, and therefore we will use this method to measure the impact of the cooperative and agricultural credit bank in economic growth in the Republic of Yemen and this method is called the Bounds Testing Approach method of joint integration, which is based on the use of this self-registration method. The Autoregressive Distributed Lag Model (ARDL) is a non-biased method that avoids many standard problems, especially reduction of views. Approach the Bounds Testing is commonly used in recent years, it has contributed to the development of this approach both of Pesaran and Smith, 1998, and Pesaran (2001).

This method has many advantages, the most important of which are:

- 1 - Impartiality and efficiency and avoid standard problems in time series that are characterized in particular by the lack of views, and this is obverse of most traditional joint integration tests which require that the sample size be large in order to the results are more efficient.
- 2- It can be applied regardless whether the variables are under the study is an integral from the zero grade, i.e. (0) I or integrated from the right one grade, i.e. (1) on condition of being I provided that they are not integrated from the grade I (2).
- 3- The ARDL form takes an enough numbers of slowdown period to obtain on the best set of data.
- 4- To identify the extent of the existence of a joint integration between the dependent variable and the independent variables in the short and long term together.

5- Determining the size and significance of the effect that the independent variables exert in the explanation of the dependent variable's behavior.

Three indicators were excluded after doing some tests because they were not significant, which is the capital proportion, the proportion of fixed assets, and the proportion of financial investments. Therefore, the cooperative and agricultural credit bank variables most influential in banking development were analyzed and studied, which is:

- 1- Total of the real customer deposits.
- 2- 2- Total of loans, facilities and real financing activities.
- 3- 3- Total of bank balances in real banks.

For the purpose of testing, the study hypothesis and depending on the fundamental in this topic by using the self- registration form. Autoregressive Distributed Lag Model (ARDL) of distributed slowdown. The equation is formulated as follows:

$$Y = f(X1, X2, X3) \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Whereas:

Y: Indicates economic growth, expressed in real GDP.

X1: represents the proportion of customer real deposits total to GDP in real prices.

X2: represents the bank's total balances in banks in real prices to GDP.

X3: represents loans total, facilities and fixed financing activities to the gross domestic product.

Pesaran and A11 (2001) presented this modern approach to testing the presence of a joint integration (verifying the existence of a balance relationship between study variables), in light of unrestricted mistake correcting (UECM) using the method of testing limits based on equation No.

(1) According to the following formula:

$$\Delta(Y_t) = c + \lambda_1 Y_{t-1} + \beta_1 x1_{t-1} + \beta_2 x2_{t-1} + \beta_3 x3_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^p a_{1,i} * \Delta Y_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^k a_{2,i} * \Delta(x1_{t-i}) + \sum_{i=0}^k a_{3,i} * \Delta(x2_{t-i}) + \sum_{i=0}^k a_{4,i} * \Delta(x3_{t-i}) + \mu_t$$

(2).....

Note: The misleading part is the long-term relationship to reach to a joint integration equation while the other side represents the short-term relationship.

Whereas:

Δ : indicates the first difference.

: C & α_0 the fixed limit.

P: maximum to period of time lags.

$\beta_1, \dots, \beta_3$: It is the ability of independent variables to slow one year in the level that can be used to reach to the inclination of the ability of the independent variable in the joint integration form (long-term relationship).

λ : The ability of the dependent variable to slow down a year in the level, and representing the long-term relationship (its terms - the condition that is required must be negative and the condition sufficient moral) in order to say that there is a long-term relationship, which is the percentage of short-term mistake that can be corrected at one time In order to return to the long-term equilibrium position, and if it is positive, it is not possible to return to the long-term equilibrium position. And if it is not significant but negative, the negative sign does not mean because λ in this case does not differ from zero and there is no long-term relationship.

Direct time μt Random mistake

Results of estimate ARDL form

First: Unit Root test

Augmented Dickey Fuller ADF test Table No. (1)

Variable	First difference			level		
	Without a timetable	Timetable	Partition	Without a timetable	Without a timetable	Partition
Y	-6,244998	-7,256975	-6,261286	0.439295	0,488776	-1,643041
Critical value 5%	-1,949319	-3,526609	-2,936942	-1,949097	-5,23623	-2,935001
Customer Deposit X1	-6,244998	-4,288133	-4.36583	-0,299120-	-2,085988-	-1,078962
Critical value 5%	-1,949319	-3,536601	-2,943427	01,949097	-3,523623	-2,935001
balance X2	-6,652083	-6,692725	-6,795991	0,375161	-1,454637	-0,809509
Critical value 5%	-1,950117	-3,536601	-2,943427	-1,950117	-3,536601	-2,943427
Loans and facilities X3	-6,244998	-6,193739	-6,228244	0,340701	-1,614070	-1,297653
Critical value 5%	-1,949319	-3,526609	-2,936942	-1,949097	-3,523623	-2,935001

Here through Table No. (1), we note that the value of t-statistic at the level (level) is less than the profit at 5% in all variables, therefore it will accept hypothesis, which says all variables in the level contains the root of a unit and the alternative hypothesis, which says that doesn't contain the root of a unit, it means that the series is unstable which means false decline at level ,but it became stable at the team 1st difference at intercept, whereas statistic according to table in all variables are bigger than amount at 5% therefore, we can be say the study variables became stable any integrated from rank 1.

Second: Estimate the lag self-registration of the distributed self-reliability:

When estimating the form and because it is concerned with lag, we can say that this method is very sensitive to the number of lag of the dependent variable and the independent variables. Whether it has two variables, dependent and other independent, it is slow both of them different way. For example, the current study, there are three independent variables, and therefore the form will slow each variable differently, meaning that it takes a sufficient number of periods of time defaults to obtain the best estimate, and therefore the lag that were identified for the variables were determined by the ARDL form as we note that the fixed limit (c) Moral and consequently, there is a joint integration relationship as follows:

Table No. (2) Number of lags based on Schwarz Bayesian standard

Y	X1	X2	X3
4	3	1	4
C	Prob		
	0.049		

Source: Table No. (2) In the appendices by based on. Eviews9 program

Through Table No. (2), we note that with the ARDL form, the lag was determined for each variable separately, whereas the dependent variable was lag by a number of 4, while the independent variables were slowing each other different from the other, so we see that the deposits total were the number of lag 3, while loans Total and financing activities were the number of lag 1, while the bank's balances total in banks is the number of lag 4.

Third: co-integration test using ARDL form:

Bound test:

This test aims to verify the existence of a joint integration relationship between all variables of the independent study as an indicator of growth and banking development to the gross domestic product as an indicator of economic growth, and Pesaran and A11 (2001) presented a recent approach to test the extent of the balance relationship verifying between the variables under the error correction form restriction (UECM), this method is known as the method of testing the boundary approach and is called the Wald test, which is based on the F Statistic distribution.

Table No. (3) The Wald Test for Joint Integration in the Long Term

ARDL Bounds Test		
Null Hypothesis: No long-run relationships exist		
Test Statistic	Value	K
F-statistic	4,378917	3
Critical Value Bounds		
significance	I0 Bound	I1 Bound
10%	2.72	3,77
5%	3.23	4,35
2.5%	3,69	4,89
1%	4,29	5,61
R2	Coefficient	
	0,94834	

Source: Table No. (3) In the appendices by relying on. Eviews9 program

To discover the existence of a synchronous integration between the study variables, that is, a long-term, balanced relationship, we compare the F Statistic value calculated with values of the special table of the Bounds Test within the framework of the Wald test found in Table no. (3) and these values are fixed and vary according to the number of capacities or time series of independent variables, and in this The study number of independent variables $K = 3$.

Through Table No. (3), we note that at the level of significance of 5%, the calculated F Statistic is slightly larger than the F Statistic, and here we reject the null hypothesis that says that there is no long-term relationship between economic growth represented by the gross domestic product Y and banking growth represented by a bank Cooperative and agricultural credit expressed in several variables (X1, X2, X3) and we accept the alternative hypothesis which says that there is a relationship but a weak relationship during the long term period between the variables moving from the independent variables to the dependent variable and may take 10-15 years.

The value of the determination coefficient (R2) to rising the explanatory strength of the independent variables of interest (0.94). Also, the value of the F-statistic indicates the quality of the form as a whole statistically.

Fourth: Estimation of the ECM error correction form:

In this test, the short-term relationship between the dependent variable and the independent variables is revealed, and it does not differ from the Johansson test in the error correction coefficient except with the number of lags, as in this test, it varies from variable to another as in the following table:

Table No. (4) Results of estimating long-term transactions and error correction form according to
ARD

ARDL Cointegrating And Long Run Form		
Cointegrating Form		
Variable	Coefficient	Prob .
CointEq(-1 (	-0,016816	0,5976
Long Run Coefficients		
Variable	Coefficient	Prob .
+Cointeq = Y - (-44.1914*X1 + 636.6511*X2 -361.7499*X3 -3160827667,5198)		
X1	-44,191416	0,6250
X2	636,651131	0,6207
X3	-361,749872	0,6399

Source: Table No. (4) In the appendices, based on. Eviews9 program

Through Table No. (4), we note that the limit or coefficient of error correction (CointEq (-1) is a negative signal, which is, as I mentioned earlier in the equation, which is λ but not significant, and therefore the necessary condition was achieved because it is negative and the sufficient condition was not achieved any The significance, and accordingly it can be said that there is no relationship between the variables in the short term means that 1.016% of the short-term errors cannot be corrected at one time in order to return to the long-term equilibrium.

As for the variables under study in the long term and through, a test showed the significance of each variable separately, to show the relationship of each variable separately to the dependent variable, as it turned out to be insignificant.

Fifth: The standard model quality test with the residual examination tests (differences or error tests):

First: Serial Correlation LM Test:

It is a complementary test of the ARDL form and uses a serial correlation LM Test to verify the quality of the form used in the study, and the study variables are the proportion of gross domestic product to total of customer deposits, the total proportion of gross domestic product to loans and facilities and financing activities and the proportion of gross domestic product to total of Bank balances in other banks.

Table No. (5) Residual examination tests (self-correlation problem)

Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test		
F-statistic	Prob	0,2366

Source: Table No. (5) In the appendices by depending on program. views9

Here in the Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test, the null hypothesis says that there is no serial self-correlation of errors, and the alternative hypothesis says that there is a serial self-correlation of errors.

Here we note through table no. (5) That the Prob is high and greater by 5%, and here we accept the null hypothesis that there is no serial self- correlation of errors and reject the alternative hypothesis.

Second: Heteroskedasticity Test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey:

Table No. (6) Residual examination test (the difference in variance)

Heteroskedasticity Test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey		
F-statistic	Prob	0.9438

Source: Table No. (6) In the appendices, based on. Eviews9 program

Heteroscedasticity Test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey 0.9438 Prob F-statistic.

Through table No.(6), this test is also one of the complementary tests to ensure the appropriateness of the model used, and in this test it reveals whether the model contains a problem of variation of

variance and here is the null hypothesis that there is no problem of variance variation i.e. that the variance of errors is homogeneous There is no problem of difference of variance in the error limit, while the alternative hypothesis says that there is a problem of difference of variance and therefore we accept the null hypothesis because the Prob for F-Statistic is very high and close to one.

Third: The Natural Distribution of Random Errors Jarque - Bera (JB):

Here in the Jarque - Bera test, which is a continuation of the residual tests, which is the test of the normal distribution of random errors. The null hypothesis that random errors are not distributed naturally or the alternative hypothesis says that the random errors are distributed naturally. Here we note that the prob is higher and greater by 5% and here we accept the null hypothesis that the random errors are not distributed naturally and we reject the alternative hypothesis.

From the above it is clear that the ARDL form is an ideal form where there are no problems, it represents the long-term relationship, errors can be corrected in the long term, there is no serial link of errors and there is no difference in the variance of the error limit.

It is also clear from the above after conducting standard tests according to the form used that the effect of banking development represented by the Cooperative and Agricultural Credit Bank on economic growth in the Republic of Yemen during the period (1995-2015) was relatively weak and needed a strong push in order to rise and be more effective.

Conclusion

Through the study and after the data analyzing under study, a number of results were reached, namely:

1. The GDP in the year 2015 increased by a growth rate of 1,092% about the year 1995, while the gross national product increased by 1,115%.

2. When the data studying of the Cooperative and Agricultural Credit Bank, the results indicated that the capital rate in the year 2015 increased by 5700% of the year 1995, while the growth rate during the period after the bank's transformation into a comprehensive bank, i.e. during the period (2005-2015) The increase in the amount in the year 2015 was 275% compared in the year 2005, and the net profit increased in the year 2015 with a growth rate 5464% of the year 1995, while the assets total has increased by 11,495% in the year 2015 of the year 1995, while increase in the rate of growth of 1,185% in the year 2015 compared to the year 2005, and as for the volume of balances in local and foreign banks, it has increased by 1,953% in the year 2015 compared to the year 1995, whereas The increase in the growth rate in the year 2015 of the year 2005 reached 109%.

The growth results of the loans total, facilities and financing activities indicate that they increased in the year 2015 by 4818% of the year 1995 and by an average of 327% of the year 2005. As for the customer deposits total, the growth rate in the year 2015 of the year 1995 increased by 26,799%, and for the year 2005 increased by 1,321%, this reflects the extent of development during the study period (1995-2015) in addition to the amount of activity that the bank plays as one of the Yemeni banking agencies.

3. through the measurement analyzing of the long-term relationship of the ARDL form, it was found that there is no long-term relationship between the variables of banking development represented by the cooperative and agricultural credit bank individually and economic growth represented by the gross domestic product, except that through the Bound test, it appeared that the relationship was weak during Long –term, which may take years to shock, to adapt between banking and economic growth.

4. Through measuring of the short-term relationship using the Error correction form, the results indicated that the short-term banking development represented by the Cooperative and Agricultural Credit Bank has no effect on economic growth in

Yemen, in addition to that the error correction coefficient [ECT (-1)] is statistically insignificant with signal the expected negative for it, and this may indicate that there is no integral relationship between the variables that the parameter [ECT (-1)] is equal to (-0.016), which means that -0.016% of deviations or errors cannot be corrected during the short-term period and that deviations from

long-term economic growth have been corrected with a time period of 10 years. This indicates that the adjustment to growth was relatively slow in the form.

5. The study showed the general trend of growth. Increasing the capital balance of the banking system and the development of technology over the long-time lead to an increase in economic growth.

6. The occurrence of the change of the cooperative and agricultural credit bank from a specialized agricultural bank to a comprehensive bank had a positive impact on the bank whereas the development in the long term even if it was weak, but it had an effective role in service providing to more segment of society and increase in The number of products in line with developments and competitiveness.

7. Due to the change in the bank's directions from investing in the agricultural sector only to commercial banking investment in the middle of the year 2004, meaning that the study contained two terms which are before change and after change, this led to a weak relationship between banking development represented by the cooperative and agricultural credit bank Economic growth is represented by the gross domestic product.

In summary, the above results revealed that the weak banking development represented by the Cooperative and Agricultural Credit Bank did not play an important role in encouraging economic growth in Yemen during the period (1995-2015) may be due to the state taking a policy of financial restraint, and that the political and economic conditions of unstable had a role. For this reason, the null hypothesis is acceptable here, which means that weak banking development was not an important factor for promoting and developing economic development in Yemen.

Recommendations:

Through these results, the study recommends that targeted policies must be taken that seek to activate the role of the banking system in the overall process of economic development in Yemen, including:

1. Reducing restrictions on the banking system in the sense of freeing the banking system from all financial restraint policies.
2. Activating and developing the role of the private sector in the economy.
3. Activating the bank's role in attracting significant personal and government savings.

4. Reducing the role of financial investments in the informal economic activities of the private sector in the economy.
5. Achieving security and political stability in Yemen.
6. Carrying out studies for investment projects managed by the bank so that they are in line with the needs of the country and through which other investments can be financed and loans are expanded.
7. Developing banking operations systems in line with the new economic conditions in the country and amending the conditions and rates for lending granting.
8. Enhancing the role of scientific research within the monetary authority in the aim of information providing that will help the bank's management in taking its decisions and help investors and clients in their decisions, as well as serving researchers in the banking field, and through this it is possible to work on a study of new projects that are compatible with the requirements of the labor market and are compatible with The state conditions and providing it to young graduates with soft loans.

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Adnan

Mona

Maniyassouwe

Farhan

Authors details:

ariqimona@gmail.com.

1 Adnan Alsanoy: Associate proffoser Agriculture collage, Sana’a University, Yemen

2 Mona Alariqi, 2ManiyassouweAmana Phd candidate ates in :economic school, Wuhan University of Technology, Wuhan, China.

3 Farhan Aslam :Assistant proffoser, Management services wing, Establishment Division Islamabad. Pakistan.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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